

P97 | The influence of *Bacillus subtilis* on reproductive indicators of chickens in the second phase of productivity

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In breeding poultry, forced molting is used to extend the life of hens. The purpose of this research was to increase the reproduction rate of kross Hisex-Brown hens in the second phase of productivity after forced molting. After the first phase of productivity, the hens were forced to molt. Two groups were formed: the control group (CONTR, $n = 1070$) and the experimental group (EXP, $n = 1068$). The feeding and housing conditions were the same, except that hens in EXP were fed an additional probiotic, based on *Bacillus subtilis* in the amount of 0.3% of weight of food. The experiment lasted for 67–82 weeks. Egg production for laying hen over the period was 80.2 pcs. in CONTR and 82.7 pcs in EXP. The average productivity in CONTR was 67.7% and in EXP 68.9%. It was found that a number of parameters improved in the experimental group: clean eggs by 1.8%, the content of vitamin A in the yolk of the egg by 16%, fertilization by 1.0%, hatching by 1.4%, hatchability by 1.22% compared with CONTR. Feed consumption in EXP decreased by 4%. The increase in productive and reproductive indicators of laying hens was associated with the use of probiotic based on *Bacillus subtilis* in the second phase of productivity. The number of microorganisms/g in the large intestine increased in EXP compared to CONTR: *Lactobacillus* 100'000 in EXP and 1'000 in CONTR, *Bifidobacterium* 1'000'000'000 in EXP and 1'000'000 in CONTR, respectively. Improving reproductive performance of laying hens in the parent flock in the second phase of productivity is possible by feeding probiotics based on *Bacillus subtilis*.

P98 | Chemotactic activity in the follicular and oviductal fluid is independent on progesterone level in porcine

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Chemotaxis has been associated mainly to progesterone (P4). However, follicular fluid (FF) and oviductal fluids (OF) have several components (cyclic guanosine monophosphate, cyclic adenosine monophosphate, atrial natriuretic peptide) with chemotactic ability. The aim was to investigate the higher chemotactic activity by serial dilution curves of FF and OF in sperm. Perioviulatory OF and FF were collected and P4 (ng/ml) concentration was measured. The serial

dilution curves were: FF (%): 0.13%(P4:0.58), 0.25(1.1), 0.5(2.18), 1(4.36) and 1.5(6.5); OF(%): 0.13(0.007), 0.25(0.013), 0.5(0.025), 1(0.051) and 1.5(0.08). The best dilution curve from each fluid was selected and its effect was studied. A chemotaxis system consists of two wells (A and B). Six wells (A) were filled with fresh washed sperm (20×10^6 /ml diluted in 500 μ l) from fertile boars ($N = 3$). The opposite wells (B) were filled with TALP (control group) and TALP supplemented with corresponding chemoattractants concentration (FF and OF). After 20 min of chemotaxis, the sperm from wells B were evaluated. The results show that 0.25% FF (7.6%) and 0.25% OF (8.4%), attracted a higher sperm percentage than their respective dilution curves and TALP (FF and OF: 0.13, 0.5, 1, 1.5 and TALP ($p < 0.05$)) that attracted around 5% of sperm in each curves and TALP. However, no difference was observed for the best dilutions curve: 0.25% FF: 6.7% and 0.25% OF: 7.1% ($p > 0.05$), even so, both fluids attracted more sperm vs TALP (5.8%) ($p < 0.05$). Concluding, other components in these biofluids could be more important than P4 in sperm attraction. Supported by Fundación Séneca, Saavedra Fajardo (20020/SF/16). MINECO-FEDER (AGL 2015-66341-R).

P99 | The effect of isoflurane anesthesia on the cardiac activity and contractility of pregnant rabbit uterine

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The aim of the study was to assess the effect of inhalation anesthesia on the cardiac activity of the female (F) and fetus and the contractility of the uterus. Isoflurane was used as anesthetic at a concentration of 2.0 vol% in an oxygen-air mixture at a gas flow rate of 1.5 l/min. The accuracy and stability of the dose of isoflurane was provided by the mini-evaporator "MINIVAP-20". Pregnant Chinchilla rabbits were included (weight 3.0 – 3.8 kg). In all F on day 30 of pregnancy by single-stage infusion into the ear vein with 1 U of oxytocin. In 10 F of the experimental group (EG), 10 min after induction of labor, inhalation mask anesthesia with isoflurane was performed for 20 min. The 10 F of the control group (CG) did not undergo anesthesia after administration of oxytocin. Electrodes were implanted to all F the day before to simultaneously record the electro-myographic activity of the uterus, the electro-cardiography (ECG) of the F and the fetuses. Indicators were recorded every 10 min. The contractile activity of the uterus was assessed by the number and duration of one contraction. Induction of labor with oxytocin in the CG at the 10th min led to the most significant increase in the number of uterine contractions by 20 times and their duration by 8 times, as well as